

FIBER ROTATION OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE LAMINATE UNDER TENSILE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are gradually replacing the status of conventional composites as a preferred solution for the high-volume production and economical demands of aviation industry. For the outstanding ductility of the thermoplastic matrix, this kind of composites can exhibit larger deformation which allows a higher possibility for the fibers to rotate during the loading. Fiber rotation is more influential in thermoplastic composites. Several researches have put effort for exploring this effect by experiments or modelling, but it still remains a considerable challenge. In this work, a tensile loading was conducted to a carbon fiber (AS4)/ thermoplastic Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) composite laminate. This study observed the specimen during the test and after fracture, to characterize the damage mechanism, especially the fiber rotation. For the laminates under tensile loading, the interfacial features of $0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ plies and $90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ plies delamination are definitely different. A significant 'white stripe' is observed at the boundary of 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies when approximately 70% tensile strength is reached. The off-axis plies deflected under tensile loading, the rule of the fiber rotation direction follows the principle of deformation compatibility with adjacent plies.

1 INTRODUCTION

The carbon-fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite (CFTPC) is being widely used in recent years [1] for its outstanding performance in impact resistance and energy absorption [2], in contrast with conventional thermosetting composite materials. Owing to the fact of no chemical changes during consolidation, CFTPC can be recycled and repaired quicker which meets the more economic and environmental-friendly production demands.

With the increasing use of these materials, the need for detailed understanding of their deformation and damage mechanisms becomes significant. Taking into account the composition of continuous fiber reinforced composite, the behaviors under different loading cases can be divided [3-6]. The main response of the unidirectional laminate under longitudinal loading is controlled by fiber, in contrast, large nonlinear deformation and subsequent matrix-dominated failure may occur during the transverse or shear loading. It's well-known that composites based on thermoplastic resin show more non-linear behavior as a result of plasticity or microscopic cracks, which leads to lower stiffness and larger deformation, makes them different from those based on thermosetting resin that reveal brittleness generally. In addition, the influence of fiber rotation for the non-linear behavior of the $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$ carbon/epoxy laminates is unneglectable [7][8]. During tensile loading, the fiber rotation between adjacent plies with different fiber orientation will extend the matrix cracks, results in interply delamination. Therefore, thermoplastic matrix composite, that shows more ductile behavior and allow higher strains, is expected to bear high fiber rotation [9].

The main aim of this paper is to evaluate the effect and investigate the causes of fiber rotation for the carbon-fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite of AS4/PEEK laminates.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENT

The specimens in this work were manufactured from unidirectional carbon fiber (AS-4D)/polyether-ether-ketone (PEEK) tape with 59% fiber by volume. Thermoplastic composite laminate plates

with 20 plies were fabricated by stacking unidirectional plies in the desired orientation into a picture frame mold before transferred to a heated platen press. For the consolidation cycle, laminated plates were heated at a constant pressure until approximately 370-400°C and held for 30 min under 7 bar pressure. Then, the composite plates were cooled to room temperature at 5 °C/min cool-down rate.

Rectangular specimens with dimensions of 250mm×25mm×2.8mm were cut from the laminate plates using a CNC milling machine. Bonded tabs (56mm×25mm×1.5mm) were used to introduce the force into the specimen and prevent the premature failure.

Tension tests were conducted based on ASTM D3039[10] at a displacement rate of 2mm/min on the testing machine with a loadcell of 100kN. Both the load and displacement were recorded during the loading process.

The optical microscopy with camera was equipped at the side of the specimens to observe the interply change during the tensile test. The fracture surface was also examined using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 TENSILE LOADING ON LAMINATE

Fig. 1 shows the load-displacement curve and the stress-strain curve of the laminate under tensile loading. The maximum deformation value of the specimen is 9.25mm and then broken at 87835N. The deformation is relatively larger than traditionally composites. As is shown in Fig. 1(b), the stress-strain curve is almost linear with the elastic modulus of 62.6GPa and the strength of 1204.6MPa. The reason for the linear relationship between stress and strain is the 50% volume fraction of 0° plies in this laminate, where the carbon fibers withstood greater stress.

The side views of the specimen during the test are shown in Fig.2. Due to the different exposure levels, the boundary line between 0° and ±45° plies is relatively more visible than that between 90° and ±45° plies before the test, as shown in Fig. 2(a). At the beginning phase of the loading, there is no obvious change in the side view of the sample. With constant loading, when approximately 70% tensile strength is reached, significant ‘white stripe’ is observed at the boundary of 90° and ±45° plies, in Fig. 2(b). These stripes appear and extend gradually, eventually forming the delamination (Fig. 2(c)). The features of 0°/±45° plies delamination and 90°/±45° plies delamination are absolutely different. Compared to 90°/±45° plies delamination, the delamination between 0° and ±45° plies is definitely clear-cut. While the delamination between 90° and ±45° plies is always zigzag and connected with intralaminar fractures. As is shown in Fig. 2(c), all the crack angles in 90° ply are almost 45°, which means shear failure mode are occurred within these plies.

(b)

Figure 1: (a) Load-displacement curve and (b) stress-strain curve of the laminate.

(a) $\sigma = 0MPa$

(b) $\sigma = 843.2MPa$

(c) $\sigma = 1204.6MPa$

Figure 2: Side views during tensile test.

3.2 FRACTOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

For a deeper understanding of different failure modes within each ply after fracture, SEM fracture surface images are shown in Fig. 3. Most of the fibers in 0° ply exhibited tension failure wrapped tightly with the PEEK matrix (Fig. 3(a)). This phenomenon, on the one hand, supports the fact that PEEK is more ductile than traditionally resin, on the other hand results from the higher processing temperature and pressure. In addition, the state of fiber and matrix has a significant meaning in modelling the interfacial properties of this material. Fig. 3(b) shows a broken layer (45°) and its adjacent layer (90°), the fracture surfaces of these plies are parallel to the fiber. Generally speaking, under tensile loading, the 90° ply will crack in a form of matrix-dominated failure with a fracture surface perpendicular to loading direction [11][12]. While Fig. 2(c) has shown that all the crack angles of the 90° ply are 45° and Fig. 3(b) definitely exhibits shear zone between the 45° and 90° ply. From these images we can confirm that the 90° ply in this laminate has been subjected to the shear force resulting from the fiber rotation of adjacent 45° ply during the tensile loading.

Figure 3: SEM images of (a) fiber pull-out and (b) matrix shear failure.

3.3 FIBER ROTATION

To explore the causes of the above ‘white stripe’ and explore how the fiber rotated during the test, the interfaces of $0^\circ / 45^\circ$ and $90^\circ / -45^\circ$ plies are magnified by the optical microscopy respectively, in

Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. The yellow solid line represents the initial fiber orientation, while the dashed line shows the final fiber orientation of the off-axis ply ($\pm 45^\circ$), the yellow arrow indicates the direction of fiber rotation. The figures also show the loading direction with red arrows. The fiber of the off-axis ply tends to deflect in the direction parallel to loading direction in Fig. 4. While the fiber of the -45° ply in Fig. 5 tends to deflect approach the direction perpendicular to loading direction. That is to say, for AS4/PEEK laminates under tensile loading, the fiber orientation of off-axis plies will deflect, the rule of the fiber rotation direction follows the principle of deformation compatibility with adjacent plies.

Figure 4: Fiber rotation between 0° and 45° plies

Figure 5: Fiber rotation between 90° and -45° plies

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, an experimental programme was conducted to characterize the damage mechanism of AS4/PEEK laminate under tensile loading. The results can be summarized as follows:

- AS4/PEEK laminate shows large deformation until final failure. When 70% tensile strength is

reached, significant ‘white stripe’ is observed at the boundary of 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. The stripes appear and extend gradually, eventually forming the delamination.

- The features of $0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ plies delamination and $90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ plies delamination are absolutely different. The delamination between 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies is definitely clear-cut, while the delamination between 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies is always zigzag and connected with intralaminar fractures.
- In 0° plies, the fiber exhibited tension failure wrapped tightly with the PEEK matrix. In 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, materials broke in a matrix-dominated mode. All the crack angles within the 90° ply are 45° resulting from the shear force applied by adjacent $\pm 45^\circ$ plies.
- Under tensile loading, the fiber orientation of AS4/PEEK off-axis plies will deflect, the rule of the fiber rotation direction follows the principle of deformation compatibility with adjacent plies.

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